

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE EDUCATIONAL MOTIVE IN ADOLESCENCE

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Annotation: today, most people feel Wayward or isolated. These emotions affect a person's health and life. Pathlessness and isolation are not only personal problems, but also social phenomena. In this article, we will talk in detail about what pathlessness and isolation are, their causes, consequences and ways to overcome.

Keywords: loneliness, isolation, mental disorders, health.

In psychology, causative motives that motivate an individual to perform mental, practical action and behavior are inextricably linked with the satisfaction of certain needs. As can be seen from the definition, their main function is to act on the reasons (factors) that motivate a person to act, to carry out behavior, to act as internal forces. In order to move this situation to educational activities, it is important to interpret the following reality: let's imagine that a math lesson is going, in the process, the attention of all adolescents is focused on a notebook, on the performance of a given task, concentrated on it and centralized. The goal of all of them is to solve the task (issue) set if it is the only one. But despite the general nature of the goal, the motives of educational activities in them have a different appearance, such as:

- getting an "excellent" or "good" grade;
- to please his parents with what he has achieved;
- to the praise of the teacher, to be awarded tahsini;
- the assignment (matter) that aroused interest in it;
- the presence of a desire to be literate;
- the social and practical significance of the educational subject;
- role in the formation of professional qualities;

Similar cases are unlikely to occur anywhere in the activity of mastering the materials of the educational subject. For a teacher who sets the main goal of improving the effectiveness of teaching, indifference towards educational motives

of adolescents is never possible, since World psychologists who have studied the problem of certain reading motives about the feelings, internal mental experiences, desires and desires of any lesson recipient find it necessary to distinguish them into two categories or groups. The motives related to the first category are directly harmonized with the content, essence of educational activities and its processes, conditions.

The system of motives falling into the second category depends on the large-scale interaction of adolescents with the environment, their need to enter into treatment with strangers, strangers, their personal view of the reality of social life. A system of motives inextricably linked with the content of educational activities can be conditionally divided into two groups, which can be called positive (positive, positive) and negative (negative, negative). The main goal from the use of such terms is to identify psychological mechanisms capable of making sharp mental turns under the influence of a local tradition, social experience (an impressive strong external factor at the level of stereotyping) extreme case.

Usually negative (negative) motivation can arise in such a situation when a teenager realizes what frustrating situations the consequence of not mastering knowledge leads to (punishment, parental reprimand, classmates, objection, receiving bad grades, discrediting among team members, etc.) and ana to carry out efforts accordingly. A teenager or student with negative motivation will continue to participate in the educational process by choosing a less distressing (difficult situation) path. Adolescents and students involved in such reading motivation will not have high performance, the opportunity to master successfully, since the lack of passion for training, the feeling of attending a lesson, the lack of knowledge and interest in the subject of study serve as a meaningful barrier to this. As a result of this, the ranks of the adoptive, loosely assimilating, sluggish students become more and more broad, something that can grow to a stereotypical level if it becomes a daily habit. Independent and successful reading, on the other hand, dictates active, rigorous, creative searches from the individual and puts similar requirements before the adopter. The unpreparedness of the individual for these situations, due to the limited possibilities in it, leads to the completion of a row of incompetents, two years of study in one class or course, with those difficulties, he completes his class, course. Adolescents in such a category can achieve positive results at the expense of restructuring the motivation of educational activities. Negative motivation towards reading in adolescents does not arise at once, but is influenced by several characteristic factors that cause it ehtimol. Ma students of the first class, college,

academic Lyceum, enter the class with a very strong desire, interest, high noble intentions. All of them have the need to take their place as students in the tevarak-environment and social environment, generating a passion to carry out certain activities in a new situation. Regardless of the new situation, specific demand, rules, relationship environment, whether a first grader or a teenager, any of them is interested in reading, feels responsibility and reacts conscientiously, positively. But in the educational process, the positive attitude towards reading in some of the adolescents begins to fade gradually. A new environment, obligations in the circles of science, positions, law and order go to lose their significance, the characteristic of relative novelty, a class (class) imagined as a circle of emotions, joys, acquires a supernatural appearance.

Having tried to determine the attitude of those who take lessons with regard to learning, the teacher begins to emphasize some criteria for recording what changes are taking place:

- a) delirium has arisen;
- b) conscientious approach Lost;
- C) made the habit of copying from others;
- g) learned to lie and look for excuses;
- d) has become a dropout of classes;
- e) failed independent assignments, etc.

The teacher or team of teachers applies traditional discipline techniques in relation to the negative change in adolescents or students predicted above:

- a) write a warning in diaries;
- b) to inform parents about this;
- C) report to the head of the class, the head of the school;
- g) shaming hard by taking out after class;
- h) put the issue of driving from the knowledge circle;

Such a clear reality occurs in any school, college, academic Lyceum, higher education system. What, in our opinion, are the factors that cause this problem, rather than rushing to take punitive measures? Why did such a phenomenon happen? Looking for answers to questions like this is a fair approach.

In particular, what are the motives for changes in the behavior of students and adolescents? What are the causes that generate a variable-VN attitude towards reading? What is the motivating factor for the implementation of this or that behavior in the classroom (in the classroom) and beyond?

It is impossible to apply measures and measures of pedagogical influence without a deep and perfect study of the above-mentioned motives of attitude and behavior, since it cannot be approached scientifically without determining the internal and external influence that manifests the motive as a quadruplet. It is noted that in the science of psychology there is a second way, but it is a little more complicated, nevertheless it has the opportunity to give the intended result. Usually harshness (strict discipline, exactingness), unjust punishment (where the motive of reading is ambiguous, if not learned) harm the psyche of the individual, do not provide any assistance in obtaining knowledge. toughness, even perseverance, is considered the most important quality, if the four of these or that characteristic behavior in a person is justified if the reasons for the obvious situation are deeply threatened. Classes in a class or class, that is, when they are focused on the formation of knowledge, skills and competencies, but they are aimed at a mediocre individual, in the case of which they cause several characteristic psychological states or subjective experiences. The result can lead to a cooling of interest in reading in gifted, well-assimilated, affable learners and adolescents, a gradual loss of satisfaction in the scale of information they expect, the pace of attainment. The shallow scientific novelty of the data, the uniformity of the educational method, the fact that independent training is carried out in one style reduces the sense of aspiration in the learners, the expected scientific information is not satisfied. Over a certain period of time, it remains to expect more interesting, more scientific information from training: the teacher expresses confidence in the incompetent, as a result of which he is encouraged to find a delicate mechanism that gives him a quadruple to self-test, support for a trifling achievement in time becomes a guarantee of success. Rather than as a complementary foursome to this, it grows within a different motive, with negative reading motivation under interaction evoking positive, sociocommunicative thought among the classroom (course)community to the student (teenager) generating Heights. The formation of the motives of educational activities cannot be carried out irregularly, without a plan, therefore, the management of this process should be developed from the first minutes of the school year, since as an individual grows older, the motives of his educational activities also change. The modern science of psychology places great importance on the relative inner need for knowledge and argues that with it there is an opportunity to somehow control its behavior. At the same time, special attention is paid to the problem of the formation of interest in stable knowledge in the reader (teenager). In fact, interests in stable knowledge give rise to learning

motives as a motivating four (strength), serving to ensure successful assimilation. The birth of interest in a particular area of knowledge, one or another type of activity, in a student or teenager largely determines the possibility of the formation of an individual in what way. For the same reason, it is up to the educational activities to ensure the socialization of the individual, the formation and development of his characteristics and qualities. But not every educational activity has the opportunity to develop them either, if it creates a feeling of desire to engage in the individual and satisfaction with him, such an activity will have fulfilled a developmental function. When a learning student or teenager feels an interest in educational activities, in this regard, a person achieves a certain achievement in the acquisition of educational material, the desire to engage in such activities is born. If the interest in educational activities improves and stagnates, then it will grow to the motive, and then to the motivation, and on the contrary, it may disappear completely and subside. A positive motive for reading, the emergence, stabilization of motivation is the guarantee of the success of mastering the basics of science by students and adolescents, the formation of personality.

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